

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF REDUNDANCY IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN AND THE PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the comparative research of pleonasm in three different languages English, Uzbek and Russian. The author has tried to use comparative method in his research and analyze the problems which occur in the translation process.

Key words: redundancy, pleonasm, tautology, synonyms, translation

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена сравнительному исследованию плеоназмов в трёх языках на английском, узбекском и русском языках. Автор попытался использовать сопоставительный метод в исследовании и анализировать проблемы, возникающие в процессе перевода.

Ключевые слова: речевая избыточность, плеоназм, тавтология, синонимы, перевод

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola pleonazmlarning ingliz, o'zbek va rus tillaridagi qiyosit taxliliga bag'ishlanga. Muallif izlanishi davomida qiyosiy uslubdan foydalanishga va tarjima jarayonida vujudga keluvchi muammolarni taxlil qilishga harakat qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy ortiqchalik, pleonazm, tautologiya, simonimlar, tarjima

Redundancy is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon, widely represented both in language and in speech [1-431]. We study language redundancy due to the fact that linguists started interpreting it more as a functional phenomenon [5-185]. Pleonasm and tautology are considered as the examples of redundant language, each of which has its types and different ways of word-formation.

In linguistics, the following types of pleonasm are distinguished depending on the type of units repeated in the speech stage (adverb, word, sentence):

1. Lexical pleonasms.
2. Semantic pleonasms.
3. Affixal pleonasms.
4. Lexical-affixal pleonasms.
5. Syntactic pleonasms.

If words that are synonymous or semantically close are combined as a lexical unit and have a descriptive-definite relationship, they are **lexical pleonasm**s: dog puppy (ko`ppak it, щенок), interval (interval oraliq`i, интервал времени), small microbes (mayda mikroblar, микробы).

Here, I should highlight one thing that, some pleonasm or tautological units of one language can be simple words in another, which means that translation it is very complicated process to find equivalent synonym for pleonasm. For example the Uzbek word "tuz- namak" is translated like "salt" in English and "соль" in Russian, which are just simple words.

Such tautological pleonasm often occur as a result of incomplete understanding or neglect of the meaning of the word, adding to it the Uzbek synonym of the word. Although some lexical pleonasm have a repetition of the same concept, there is a shift in meaning in the semantics of the word: head-toe sarpo (Persian "sar-po" - head-toe), lahm gosht (Arabic. «lahm» - meat) (bosh-oyoq sarpo (forscha «sar-po» — bosh-oyoq), lahm go`sht (arab. «lahm» — go`sht).

Semantic pleonasm is also common in the Uzbek language: oyoq bilan tepkilash- (kicking with the feet, пинать ногой), ko`z bilan ko`rish- (seeing with eyes, видеть своими глазами), o`z quloqlari bilan eshitish- (hear with own ears, слышать своими ушами). The semantic redundancies in these examples serve the purpose of increasing the emphasis in speech [2-8.9].

There are some cases when it is possible to find appropriate pleonastic synonym for pleonasm. So translator should be very attentive in working with redundant language.

The redundancy that occurs as a result of the repetition of semantics is called

semantic redundancy, in which the class of words belonging to different word groups and having a semantic relationship with each other forms a lexical space between groups, and repeated semantics combine in interdependence. As a result of the formation of the semantic field on the basis of a single archetype, the specific semantics of the archisema are realized and concretized, the repetition of the selected semantics is emphasized, exaggerated, emotionally expressive. For example, sometimes a person's name is preceded by a word that means his sign, while in a word in the category of a horse, his sign is clear:

One day an old man cried- (Qaysi kuni yig`lab ketdi bir mo`ysafid chol, Однажды один пожилой человек плакал).

The denotative semantics of the old lexeme are: "person", "possessing the sign of old age", "gray hair and beard", "old age". In both components of the old man's construction, the semantic field is "old age", where the old man is the archetype, that is, the general sema. This semantic field unites several semantics around the old archetype. The following semas are special semas of the old archetype and have methodological differences: old- sacred, munkillagan-nuroni, старый-пожилой. In the poetic text, the special semantics attached to the archetype are in the position of semantic redundancy and realize the content. The subject of the creative old man in the combination of "relatively old", in the combination of the old man "much older", in the combination of the old man "very old", in the combination of the enlightened old man "bright face", in the combination of the blessed old man "very respectable". In this case, the special semantics attached to the archetype are in the position of semantic redundancy [4].

Affixal pleonasm occurs as a result of repetition of suffixes: (kuyla-shaylik, kuyla-ylik, давай споём песню, let's sing, ko`k-imtir-roq, голуб-оват-ый, blu-ish), and so on.

In **lexical-affixal** pleonasm, the meaning of the root is repeated again by the suffix. For example, at the heart of the words to`g`ayzor, o`rmonzor is the meaning of both place and community. The words pleonastic are also used in the words potter, warehouse, dormitory. In such cases there is no need for pleonastic use [3.97].

As a conclusion we can say that, we can come across with some differences while translating redundant words. So in order to analyze this viewpoint, we have done research in three languages English, Uzbek and Russian and discussed problematic points in the translation process. Sometimes redundancy can be translated into a simple word and this process demands high experience and knowledge from translator.

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